

Edible Cities Network – Integrating Edible City Solutions for social, resilient and sustainably productive Cities

Annual conference report

Deliverable D1.5

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Authors:

Stadt Andernach (ANDERNACH): Iris Kroeger

Gemeente Rotterdam (ROTTERDAM): Mohamed el Massoudi, Katelien van den Berge, Helmi Hansma

Oslo Kommune (OSLO): Stephanie Degenhardt

Gallis Helene (NABOLAGSHAGER): Laura Martinez

Universitaet fuer Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU): Maximilian Mandersheid

Fundacio Institut Catala De Recerca De L'aigua (ICRA): Joaquim Comas

Nibio - Norsk Institutt For Bioekonomi (NIBIO): Wendy Fjellstad

Royal Melbourne Institute of Technology Spain SL (RMIT): Ferne Edwards

Humboldt-Universitaet zu Berlin (UBER): Ina Säumel, Thomas Wachtel, Suhana Reddy

Quality assurance:

Humboldt Universität zu Berlin (UBER): Chiara Bearzotti

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Meeting goals and progress achieved in the project

The annual meeting of EdiCitNet was held in Girona (ES) on 22-25 October 2019 and it was hosted by our local partners ICRA and University of Girona. The conference was opened by the conference organizers, represented by Joaquim Comas (ICRA) for the EdiCitNet consortium, and the vice president of Girona University (Dr. Josep Calbo Angrill Vice-Rector for Strategic Projects) and the coordination team (UBER): Ina Säumel (Coordinator) and Suhana Reddy and Thomas Wachtel.

The EdiCitNet Coordinator informed the participants about the objectives of the project and presented what was achieved so far. The latter one include:

- Front-Runner cities (FRC) will showcase new ECS at their living labs and therefore co-create an implementation plan within the local city team.
- The experience of the FRC as permanent result flow from the Living Labs will be shared via special formats addressing the Follower Cities (FC) as cities that benefit from their experience. Furthermore, the hubs (mostly local NGOs and SMEs as well as research institutes) function with the FRC as mentoring cities for the FC. All data produced in the Living Lab will be fed into the database and are available there also beyond project-time. The FC are just starting to set-up the Transition pathways as tailor-made urban masterplans. The recent modules of the training-of-trainers (ToT) sessions provided methodological introduction for the FC. In WP5 a monitoring scheme for the Living Labs will be developed in order to analyse the impact of the living labs (especially the social impact) on the citizens and their cities.
- To set up a global network for global outreach a defined plan for communication was made. This plan foresees several communication measures throughout the project time. At the moment formats like EdiCitNet and friends but also representing the project in international conferences and workshops supported the visibility of the project in Europe and beyond. This was already successfully targeted, as the number of EdiCitNet stakeholders already increased during the first year from initially 35 partner to 150 associated partner which mainly are members of the city teams.

Prior to the meeting, the Coordination team performed an internal analysis of the main risk at project level and decided to set up a team building measure for the consortium. Additionally, the internal analysis revealed a typical trap for large scale transdisciplinary project: The silo-thinking and marginal changes of perspectives are threatening the projects impact and success. To tackle this the coordination team and the local steering group from ICRA and UDG decided to conduct an afternoon action based on smaller groups structure (details see below). Thus the motto of the Annual EdiCitNet Meeting was: Change of perspective and open up the silo-thinking.

The change of perspective was emphasized during all meetings since project start. The main aim of breaking up silo-thinking is to smoothen working processes. This is a crucial factor driving a consortium to successfully conduct a project together. The typical parameter of content management, financial safety and time schedule are not sufficient to reach out and scale up the impact of such projects. The stakeholder management and collaborative yet comprehensive understanding of the main goals of EdiCitNet have to be brought to the fore.

Team building exercise: Games of Food and Cooking

A Team Building measure was useful to boost again the team feeling within such a huge consortium. Many staff members have changed in the partner organisations since the Kick-off meeting. Thus, the team in WP8 and the local steering group (ICRA and UdG) set up a team building exercise to strengthen the team feeling but also reinforce personal connections within the consortium. We named this

exercise “Game of foods”, as Girona was one of the main settings for the series “Game of Thrones”. The team building exercise brought the participant to connect to the city and to the other team members. After the team building, the teams cooked together the dinner of the first day of the annual meeting, to emphasize also for the consortium that- as stated in the EdiCitNet proposal- “eating together brings together”.

Reports on the state-of-the-art from the work packages

Update WP1: State-of-the-art

Rapporteur: WP1 leader, Ferne Edwards (RMIT Europe)

An overview of WP1 achievements over the first year of the project with a summary of what to expect and plan for in 2020 was provided shortly. This presentation was followed by a 25-minute workshop where the cities were clustered into three groups to promote knowledge exchange across the cities to discuss the uptake of the Terms of Reference for the City Teams.

WP1 outcomes for the first year of the project include: D1.1, MS1, D1.2, D1.3, D1.4, D1.5, D1.6. Some of these outputs (D1.4, D1.6) have been reopened and are currently under revision.

In addition to:

- Organising the FRC- FC Team Meeting in May 2019.
- Supporting establishment of communication channels (WP1 newsletter, CMT for cities).
- Ongoing backstopping support for the City Teams.

Group work

While we acknowledge that a long list of questions were provided that couldn’t be completed within the short session, they opened up channels of communication on the current state of the City Teams (*Montevideo was not present), their key issues, and what clarifications and support is required to help them become stronger for the next phase of the project.

Summary of key outcomes WP1 session, Girona 2019

<p>1. WHO - Have you appointed a chair and secretary? Does your CT include representatives from all relevant sectors?</p>	<p>City Teams see the creation of the City Teams as an ongoing task that will take time, with some not wanting to start or push the process forward too quickly in case they de-incentivise and hence risk losing participation in the project. One city had not yet shared the project due to personnel change.</p>
<p>2. HOW OFTEN - Do you have regular City Team meetings? How often does your CT need to meet? Have you got a workplan including CT goals and responsibilities?</p>	<p>Most of the City Teams are having meetings. However these occur on a range of basis, some monthly, others three or four times per year, and others as required to respond to key tasks.</p>
<p>3. SHARED GOALS - Does your CT have a shared understanding of ECS, a shared vision and goals?</p>	<p>Only 4 City Teams feel that this is an iterative process that will take time and that the processes and focus of the City Team are still being established.</p>

<p>4. Reporting & CMT - Are you taking meeting minutes? Are you sharing news with CT members, EdiCitNet or the public? Are you using CMT or another online platform?</p>	<p>Most of the city teams are taking minutes of their meetings, but only a few cities are publishing news of their cities on CMT. Hesitancies to use CMT included not having enough time to post, that it's inappropriate to share minutes with the rest of the consortium, remain unclear on how to use CMT, feel is not yet relevant to post, and others ask if it is necessary to use.</p>
<p>5. RISKS - Are you monitoring risks, taking measures to address them and reporting them to EdiCitNet?</p>	<p>Few cities responded to this question, all with 'yes' as recorded in the International Context Summary Sheet report.</p>
<p>6. ASSOC. BODIES – FRCS – how does your City Team relate to your Living Lab? Do you have thematic sub-groups associated with your CT? How are they connected with CT?</p>	<p>Andernach was the only city to respond to say that their City Team is organizing both the Living Lab and other related topics.</p>
<p>7. ToRs - Have you discussed the TORs with your City Team? Do you agree with the TORs as they are? If not, what needs to change? Can you sign the ToRs now? :)</p>	<p>Few cities so far have discussed the Terms of references (ToRs) with their City Team members. Issues included: too early in the process, not wanting to upset new members, language issues, who to sign, and if they can edit the form.</p>

In upcoming workshops, the following questions could be addressed (decision pending):

- Possible engagement with marginal groups in ECS as a task of your City Team.
- Possible ECS policy integration as a task of your City Team.

Summary and next steps

- All deliverables should be completed before the end of the year.
- Format of the Letter of Commitment (LoC) is still under discussion: City representatives sign a letter expressing the support to the project and to the city team. Despite of this, city members are already active and are working on the project.
- ToRs need to be adapted: Guidelines (Terms of references) have been circulated but their form and language need to be amended to meet the needs of the city team members. Despite of this, work has started.
- Time for the submission to the Coordination of LoC and ToRs has been kept flexible with respect to the original plan indicated in D1.1 ⁽¹⁾, because the city teams are slowly coming together.
- The establishment of the city teams (e.g. by adding stakeholders) is not as static as described in the original project and further in the D1.1. Rather WP1 sees this as an ongoing dynamic process in this project.
- Draft framework and process of EdiCitNet awards, discussion to be started in January 2020 (Ref: Task 1.6 EdiCitNet network international conferences and awards. Lead: ANDERNACH)
- Contribute to project internationalisation (Ref: Task 1.4: Establishing and facilitating an active international Edible City Network. Lead: ANDERNACH)
- RMIT EUROPE to contribute strong support to other WPs 3, 5, 7 and 8.

¹ Original deadline was May 2019, as set in the D1.1 plan, page 16, but this has been changed to adapt to the dynamic of the city team growth.

Update WP2: State-of-the-art

Rapporteur: WP2 leader, Joaquim Comas (ICRA)

Several tasks have been carried out mainly regarding database structure, data collection and tools concept development. The database structure is being developed in accordance to data collection procedures (Survey and literature review) and expected outputs from the tools. Regarding data collection, the literature review on ECSs is at initial stage. The structure and questions of the EdiCitNet survey were developed in a collaborative and inclusive way.

In parallel, tools concept is being developed. Basically, two types of tools were presented during the meeting. An user-friendly **open access catalogue of ECS** focused 3 main principles: sharing knowledge, learning together and connecting ECSs. **Urban planning tools** such as the serious game and guidelines to facilitate the inclusion of ECSs in urban plans.

Interfaces to interact between WP2, WP4 and WP5 have also been established. For example, WP2 gave feedback on the initial list of indicators of WP5. In addition, WP2 crossed prioritized indicators of WP5 with survey questions. As a result, 66% and 84 % of indicators selected by, respectively, Andernach and Oslo are covered by the survey. Considering indicators selected by both cities as “core indicators”, the survey is covering 92% of them. Therefore, the survey besides feeding the database and tools of WP2, also can assist data collection in the living labs. In addition, WP2 is collaborating closely with WP4 regarding social indicators review, collection of past experiences in FCs and potential use of the tools to assist the transition pathway methodology.

Group work

The aim of the group work was to receive input and feedback on the tools concept developed so far. In other words, WP2 aimed to see if what is being developed is in accordance to potential end-users needs and expectations. And, if not, to identify the requirements of the toolbox by the different potential end-users. In this regard, we asked the following question:

- How relevant are the tools? Both tools were considered either relevant or very relevant.
- What would you like to learn from other ECSs? Main answers were related to technical information (yield, space required, soil quality, time required), how to engage people, economic factors (business models, costs and benefits, or implement and run ECS).
- What kind of recommendations do you expect to implement your ECS? Answers included: Implementation costs, selection of ECS or NBS, and implementation requirements.
- What would be the functionalities of your perfect tool? (be imaginative!) Answers included: Demographic data, social impact, organic farming practices, land availability for ECSs, open source, open database, assisting urban plan, adapted to existing data, long-term update, user friendly, facilitating sharing approaches and understandable results.
- How do you think these tools can help you to integrate ECS into your city? Answers were mostly related to the following topics: Improving green space use/Connecting ECS, presenting potential opportunities for ECS, presenting potential conflicts regarding ECS implementation and maintenance, giving arguments to foster political commitment, Showing pilot cases, Focusing on innovative ECSs, presenting one example per type of ECS in detail, and Insights on best practices (goals, scale and context).

Considering all questions, the following topics were the most cited: cost and benefits (economic factors), space requirement or area available for ECS implementation, technical requirements (implementation or maintenance), social impact (cohesion, participation, inclusion, engagement) and best practices and detailed examples.

Summary and next steps

WP2 is on track. The web-based survey is being developed as well as the concept of the tools and database structure. Next steps include: Finishing and launching survey, integration of the survey results and other ECS data to the DB, continue with conceptualization and co-design of catalogue, and

conceptualization of data, models and serious game for planning. Planning part specially in coordination with Sempeter pri Gorici, Sant Feliu de Llobregat, and testing on more cities.

Update WP3: State-of-the-art

Rapporteur: WP3 lead, Katelien van den Berge (ROTTERDAM)

The chief aim of WP3 of EdiCitNet is co-developing and co-implementation of Living Labs (LL) on innovative ECS in the EdiCitNet FRCs. These living labs with specific local contexts and typical urban challenges will provide a robust evidence base for efficacy and effectiveness of ECS. From the results and experiences of these co-developed LL will set up Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) for rapid exploitation and up-scaling in FCs and in further interested cities beyond. The first objective of WP3 is to **adjust planned Living Labs in FRC by co-design and co-development user friendly ECS**. Currently, WP3 is preparing the deliverable D3.1 Implementation Project Plans for Oslo, Rotterdam, Andernach. The LL differ in (physical) structure and consequently differ in the way the LL is developed across the project. Regular telcos are held between FRCs.

The LL description of Oslo needs to be modified because of the bottom-up decision of the members of the LL to reshape part of the text to match their actual needs. This is included in the amendment in preparation. Briefly:

- Norwegian State Housing Bank (NSHB) supports the government with realizing its social housing policy. Loans or subsidies that are given to private people cover support for housing for people who are not eligible to receive a normal loan from banks. BUT the NSHB does not work with ECS or support business start-ups and hence does not offer the service as stated in the DoA (Empower local citizens to launch their own start-up with the support of the NSHB). This needs to be changed in the DoA.
- The Farmers' Union (Bondelaget) <https://bondensmarked.no/english> is only one possible market channel, who until now has been very closed to new members, particularly outside the traditional agriculture craftsmanship. Meanwhile there are other marked channels for distribution of ECS such as the municipality itself, REKO Ring or other forms of markets that are highly relevant for EdiCitNet/ the Living Lab in Oslo. Hence we would like to open up the description in the DoA to be able to consider other, more promising, channels. This needs to be changed in the DoA.

Next steps

New staff members will join the team in the WP3 lead for Rotterdam: Helmi Hansma will take over the WP3 lead in the upcoming weeks, supported by Mariët Pors.

Some upcoming events organised by the LL are:

- 2nd Andernach Living Lab workshop, 6 November 2019, Andernach (DE). Main topics: State of implementation of the decisions of the last meeting, Exchange of experience regarding the past actions at the living lab, Planning of living lab activities in 2020 Living Lab implementation plan.
- 2nd Rotterdam Living Lab workshop, 20 November 2019, Rotterdam (NL). Main topics: Road to finalising Implementation plan LL (living document), setting the stage for the implementation phase.
- 2nd Oslo co-creation meeting, 27 November 2019, Oslo (NO). Main topics: Finalizing the Living Lab implementation plan, planning activities for 2020, Monitoring of the activities.

Update WP4: State-of-the-art

Rapporteur: Maximilian Manderscheid (BOKU)

The Transition Pathways Methodology (TPM) has been used in various contexts but never before in the field of Edible Cities. The TPM in the EdiCitNet project guides an **urban planning process that is based on systems thinking and scenario techniques**. Further details on the TPM can be found in D4.1. The timeline for the implementation of the TPM has been presented to the other WPs:

When?	What?	Aim	Output
January 2019 – December 2020	System Development (initial workshops April – July 2019)	Describing the city’s case as a complex “whole” – as a system with all stakeholders, institutions and existing ECS.	System Analysis of the respective cities including an analysis.
February 2020 – May 2021	Scenario Development (initial workshops September – November 2020)	Developing and describing diverse future scenarios that define the specific conditions under which ECSs implementation is potentially taking place.	Scenarios on different ECS.
June 2021 – March 2022	Transition Development (initial workshops June – November 2022)	Development of an activity plan for enabling the change of certain key factor attributes in order to maintain / foster existing or establish new ECS.	Activity Plans for the transition into the realization/fostering of ECS.

Challenges

In regard to the work of WP4 there are several challenges that need attention:

- The city teams are formed but in different cities the engagement varies and due to that the TPM and the planned workshops might need adaption to the different conditions in the different cities. This implicates changes in responsibilities and workload.
- As the city teams are now functional the challenge is to ensure their workability over time. This means it needs to be clarified what the city teams can and/or are willing to take on board. This is to be clarified with every city representative. Each city team is made up by a core team and additional members who are joining according to their interests/goals in the course of the project.
- The implementation of each workshop for the system development (this is the first workshop in the TPM in each FC) needs to be adapted to the individual city team requirements.
- In each city we find different constellations of city teams which also slightly challenge the WP4 lead with different schedules and agendas. Therefore, individual planning is necessary to align the understanding of the TPM process.

- According to D4.3 “Collection of existing experiences” which is due end of August 2020 a data collection plan needs to be tailored to each city, its needs and resources.

Summary and next steps

- WP4 is well on track. There is no delay foreseen.
- D4.1 has been submitted. D4.2 is in preparation.
- All partners are working and collaborating well.
- The exchange with other WPs needs to be increased regarding shared or/and overlapping tasks. Together with WP2 and 5 there needs to be a shared understanding for the collection of existing experiences of ECS.
- Together with WP2 the framework for collecting existing experiences will be set up (January 2020)
- Individual dates with the different city representatives and city teams will be set to plan the first shared workshop of the TPM “ System Development”
- A guide is created and will be sent out including specific tasks to be done before the workshop

Update WP5: State-of-the-art

Rapporteur: Wendy Fjellstad (NIBIO)

WP5 is on track. The overall objective of WP5 is to facilitate following up the performance and effectiveness of Edible City Solutions implemented in the Living Labs, in relation to their goals. We have conducted a literature review and a preliminary prioritisation of potential economic, environmental and social indicators based on feedback from the cities. This is presented in Deliverable 5.1.

Next steps

Now, as the FRC are becoming clearer about the goals and activities in their LL we need stronger dialogue with them to identify which indicators will be used in the LL and how the data should be collected and stored. We also need dialogue with WP2 regarding the design of the database, and with WP4 to ensure that our catalogue of indicators also covers the needs of FC. In addition, we have been invited to collaborate at a European level. All NBS projects supported by DG RTD and EASME have been invited to work together to harmonise approaches, methods and data. WP5 will collaborate in “Taskforce 2: Impact Assessment Framework (indicators)”. Documents and presentations about this can be found in the WP5 workspace on Sharepoint in the folder “IEF Taskforce 2”.

Mentimeter survey

We carried out a Mentimeter survey, focusing in particular on methods of data collection. We also had input to the survey from other WP and the last questions focus more on challenges to ECS implementation, policy aspects and integration of marginal groups. The “raw” results from the Mentimeter survey are available on sharepoint (pdf).

Summary

Although there wasn't much time for discussion during the session, the Mentimeter survey triggered considerable discussion afterwards. Here we summarise points from all WP5 discussions (also those on Friday's WP5 work session):

- The cities are aware of the urgency of addressing the indicators and the need to start as soon as possible. We discussed some ways to make it possible to collect the data without this being a huge burden for the city teams.

- There is general agreement that it is better to have fewer indicators that are significant to the cities and their goals, than a plethora of them that are not realistic to achieve (the Mentimeter showed some differences in perspectives between researchers and city teams views).
- Indirect methods would be good for the city teams (collect multiple data from the same collection method). BOKU mentioned the questionnaire that will be sent around to FC and FRC cities and said it could be a good platform to collect cross information between all cities (make them comparable).
- We suggested that the next WP5 meeting could focus on a single city, focusing on exactly which indicators that could be collected in that particular LL. The idea would be to make the discussion less abstract for city teams. The city teams don't believe it is a time efficient way as they are in need to start collecting data, so they suggested to focus on one/two indicators in which they could already start working on (which they will suggest).
- Berlin mentioned that it would be good to have a platform where the FC could learn from the ECS activities and experiences (tools and results).
- Finding students to help city team members collecting data seems to be a good solution for cities.
- The FRC voiced their concerns that the expectations from the project seem to be much greater than they are able to provide with the resources they are currently allocated. Although they agreed that the methods of data collection that we presented were technically feasible, they felt that it was unrealistic to expect that the City Teams should organise this data collection - that they did not have the time or manpower to use on this.
- The FRC expressed great concern that the ambitions expressed in the "Measurable Impacts" in the Grant Agreement are not at all realistic for their Living Labs. They felt that there was a conflict between the idea that the LL should evolve through co-creation and yet that "all 4 FRC" were expected to deliver so many different kinds of indicator data (economic, sustainability, biodiversity well-being etc.). The cities were of the strong opinion that they should only report indicators that are directly related to the goals of their ECS.

After this a collection of ideas about supporting formats and measures for the cities have been collected:

- City - WhatsApp Group;
- Annual City Team Meetings, with city focus and experts listening as matter of support;
- Monthly online meetings (informal without Agenda → maybe linked to the FRCs monthly meetings;
- Topic specific online meeting (with the goal to transfer information from different cities and WPs).

WP3 and 4 will evaluate and initiate these measures of support after the annual meeting.

Update WP6: State-of-the-art

Rapporteur: WP6 lead, Helene Gallis (Nabolagshager)

Stakeholder mapping

The deliverable D6.2 Stakeholder power-interest maps is in preparation. Stakeholder power-interest mappings of diverse ECS-initiatives in FRC (Oslo, Rotterdam, Andernach) are drafted, on a case studies approach, based on secondary info, interviews, observations, and looking for diversity on project maturity, scale, and orientation (PPP).

The D6.2 is a deliverable covering a comparative case study for EdiCitNet with the following goals:

- To provide insights on the importance of key actors and their stakes in the realization and continuity of ECS-initiatives;
- to connect to ECS-initiatives for later interactions on PPP-business model canvas.

So far, the cases of Oslo and Rotterdam have been analysed. The final results of the analysis will be included later in the deliver D6.2 when the analysis is extended also to FRC Andernach. The two other FRC of Berlin and Havana will be added after Berlin formally changes its role in the consortium and Havana is added to the consortium.

Group work

During the group work, Nabolagshager hosted a fast-paced and interactive workshop. The objectives of the workshop were:

- To let the project partners discover the abundant business opportunities in edible city solutions through an innovative workshop format, and
- to get them excited about going beyond the more common social and environmental objectives into business viability and job creation;
- to explore some of the key challenges uncovered during the stakeholder interview, namely that of finding supplemental/complementary products and services to make the business models of the ECS startups more resilient;
- to explore the “hive mind” of our consortium, that we as a sum are capable of generating results far beyond those of the individual members, and last but not least;
- to share a workshop format that participants can take home with them and host local workshops over variations on this topic.

The participants were split into groups centered around three tables, each with a table host, large papers and lots of markers. Each table represented one setting for the challenges, selected to feel relevant for most participants;

- A. A large piece of land on a farm on the outskirts of the city, suitable for varied crops
- B. A rooftop garden on an office building in the middle of city
- C. An herbal garden at a community center in a low-income residential area, with access to a good kitchen

The participants were then given a challenge, that each group should brainstorm around and relate to their setting, for 3 minutes, and write ideas down as a idea/mindmap.

The challenges, which can be endlessly varied to adapt to a local context, were:

- CHALLENGE A: a product that the best restaurant in town would pay a lot of money for
- CHALLENGE B: a unique experience that a tourist would pay €30-50 to participate in
- CHALLENGE C: a small product you can easily produce 1000 units of for sale
- CHALLENGE D: a service that a senior citizen would subscribe to on a monthly basis
- CHALLENGE E: a product directed at the largest immigrant groups in your area
- CHALLENGE F: how can your products or services be personalized so customers come back
- CHALLENGE G: a luxury product you can make that can be a corporate employee x-mas gift

The workshop generated an impressive wealth of ideas really demonstrating the multidisciplinary, geographic distribution, academic skill set and above all the eagerness to explore ECS business models among the participants. Some of the ideas included distilling herbal schnaps, hosting team building exercises, making organic beauty products and allowing for the adoption of vegetables from seeds to ripe vegetables. However, the importance of the workshop lies not in the list of ideas generated, but that the participants now have an improved understanding of the role of WP6 and business in ECS, and are now empowered to explore their local settings with this workshop format.

Pictures 1: Team work facing the challenges.

Update WP7: State-of-the-art

Rapporteur by WP7 lead: Thomas Wachtel (UBER)

The discussion in WP7 focussed only on the tasks related to education and training.

Introduction

With Edible City Solutions broadly anchored in society, including raising awareness and motivation of stakeholders, promoting communities of practice and supporting ECS knowledge sharing and effective policy making skills, almost every objective of WP7 is directly linked to education or knowledge transfer. The WP7 session therefore focused on the development of formats and content for innovative and exciting educational activities in the spirit of Edible City Solutions.

The session was pre-structured by a previously convened Education Taskforce (consisting of MUNDRAUB, BHFP, FSUB and UBER) and aimed to take into account the different approaches, interests and requirements within our complex civilisation. In order to represent society as the main target group of EdiCitNet at all, all tasks have worked out from the perspective of both, experts and citizens in our individual group work.

After a short summary of WP7 and an introduction to today's tasks, the practitioners of the Education Force presented well-functioning formats of their daily educational work. Building on these ideas, the consortium dealt in the following group activities first with content and later with formats that really can convince and motivate different social groups.

Group work

Contents for ECS Education

In order to cover the extensive contents of ECS in its entirety, table groups were formed on 4+1 subtopics. These topics were:

- **Legal Framework and Governance** (e.g. regulations, steering, implementation)
- **Social Impact** (e.g. networks, social integration, visibility, perception)
- **Ecological Systems** (e.g. water systems, waste, biodiversity, resources)
- **Economic Value** (e.g. job creation, reduction of public costs)

With regard to the practical implementation and fast replication of ECS, a further table group was set up for the contents of a special ECS format (ECS to go!). Here the participants should determine which contents (and their extent) are essential, if one wants to understand in 20 minutes what ECS are.

The audience was invited to assign themselves to the individual tables according to their expertise and discuss the contents together. After 20 minutes, all participants switched tables and their roles from expert to citizen and assessed and improved the outcome of the experts.

Formats for ECS Education

Formats determine not only the content but also the success of a measure. In order to develop truly innovative and meaningful formats with a really wide reach, 4 different table groups were formed to which the participants should assign according to their expertise.

- **Global** table for onsite/offline formats (e.g. excursions)
- **Local** table for onsite/offline formats (e.g. harvest events) pls. mention the city/region
- **Online** format table (e.g. MOOC, games, webinar)
- **Special** format table (feel free to find innovative formats, e.g. ECS to go!)

This time, the collected formats were to be evaluated according to their reach, attractiveness, implementation costs and user-friendliness.

Summary and next steps

This creative microcosm of many different attitudes, goals and viewpoints provided very practical and balanced results for the further development of educational formats including the EdiCitNet summer school next year (see also the contents of the concept of D7.5) As next steps the many suggestions and ideas will be evaluated by the Education Taskforce, summarised and checked for feasibility. The summary will be discussed and improved within WP7. On this basis, ECS curricula and training modules will be developed (D7.4).

Recommendations of the EC/EASME advisors

The two advisors at EASME in charge of EdiCitNet project, Piret Noukas and Galya Ivanova-Lazarova, joined us and held two presentations.

Piret Noukas (EASME, project advisor²), reminded the consortium about the **expectations the European Commission has on the EdiCitNet team**. EdiCitNet listed in the Description of the Action specific **measurable impacts** which are very beneficial for the consortium to monitor the project achievements. We can only recommend to come back to these ambitious impact expectations.

Additionally, the consortium is expected to:

- Contribute to the creation of an European reference framework and the establishment of EU leadership for NBS, new economic opportunities, new products, services, protocols etc.
- Contribute to increased awareness of the benefits of re-naturing cities, creation of communities of practice, more effective policy making and better informed decision making
- Enhanced stakeholder and citizen ownership of NBS
- Increased international cooperation and global market opportunities in non-EU countries, i.e. EU-China platform
- Implementation of EU environmental policies
- Healthier, culturally diverse and greener regenerated European Cities

Piret also highlighted the **importance of clustering with other European initiatives** such as:

- SiEUGreen – urban agriculture for food security, resource efficiency and resilient cities. In particular Piret pointed at the wish of the European Commission to see EdiCitNet and

² For the consortium partners, this presentation is available on our intranet (Sharepoint): <https://projectsworkspace.eu/sites/EdiCitNet/EdiCitNet%20Meetings%20Workshops%20and%20Conferences/Annual%20Meeting%20in%20Girona%20October%202019/WP8/Piret-Presentation.pptx> It is going to be made available in Zenodo: <https://www.zenodo.org/communities/edicitnet?page=1&size=20https://www.zenodo.org/communities/edicitnet?page=1&size=20>

SiEUGreen organising a joint session on ECS/urban agriculture at the next European Week of Cities and Regions (Oct 2020).

- Fit4Food2030 – stakeholder platform supporting FOOD 2030 policy framework
- Urbinat – regeneration and integration of deprived social housing developments through inclusive NBS, including urban vegetable gardens. *URBINAT is one of the projects who joined the Session EdiCitNet and friends on Friday.*
- proGReg – green infrastructure for post-industrial urban regeneration, includes urban farms & gardens.
- Naturvation – urban nature atlas, including urban gardens and allotments.
- FoodE – inclusive sustainable city/region food systems. Besides cities looks at the rural and coastal areas, but like EdiCitNet aims to create a database of existing innovative food solutions and build a network of stakeholders.
- FoodShift2030 – accelerated food system innovations benchmarked against state-of-the-art food system innovations by assessing their effects on a set of indicators.

The presentation of Galya Ivanova-Lazarova, EASME finance officer, focused on the importance of **avoiding common financial errors** in the implementation of a Horizon 2020-funded project.³

FRC update and presentation of Living Labs

Conceptualization and planning Max Manderscheid (BOKU), Thomas Wachtel and Suhana Reddy (UBER). Rapporteurs: WP3 team members.

Session was moderated by: Maximilian Manderscheid (BOKU), Katelien van den Berge (ROTTERDAM)

It was foreseen in Sant Feliu de Llobregat (FC) to emphasize the relation between WP3 and 4 by provide on the one hand a summary of the current state of the Living Labs but on the other hand to emphasize also the importance of the FC. Therefore, the Living Lab presentation was followed by a workshop for interconnecting the Follower Cities and the Front-Runner Cities. The aim of this session was to matchmake them and guide them to “actively seek” for “their” Front-Runner City. This matchmaking will intensify the connection and the knowledge exchange. We assume that in the upcoming year the mentoring of the FRC will be in the foreground whereas after the FC have started the Transition Pathways steps their experience of anchoring ECS as tool for resilient urban planning will in return support the FRC in learning about replication of methodological approach within the municipality. In order to not decide top down which cities should intensify their mutual learning, we decided to let the choice be with the city and give the space to find a fitting partners according to different topics. Once this exchange and contact is initiated by the cities (representatives) themselves a learning effect will start regarding which information / help / support can be found in which city (FRC or FC). We assume that this participatory way of match-making and this decision will be more sustainable and thus supports connections beyond the project-time.

During this session the following presentations were held:

³ Her presentation is available for the consortium partners in the project intranet (Sharepoint): <https://projectworkspace.eu/sites/EdiCitNet/EdiCitNet%20Meetings%20Workshops%20and%20Conferences/Annual%20Meeting%20in%20Girona%20October%202019/WP8/Galya-%20AvoidingCommonFinancialErrors%20in%20H2020.pptx> It is going to be made available in Zenodo: <https://www.zenodo.org/communities/edicitnet?page=1&size=20>

Andernach LL: The Andernach LL has a social focus and aims to include more citizens into the edible city (especially children and their families), thereby increasing environmental education and social cohesion. The main target groups are pedagogical institutions such as kindergartens, schools and youth center. The city team agrees on an annual topic and organizes cross-institutional actions and events regarding to that topic at the LL. Andernach presented some events of 2019 according to the topics “insect biodiversity” and “herbs”.

Oslo LL: The Living Lab in Oslo aims at piloting ways that combine the social and economic benefits of ECS by mobilising and empowering local, marginalized communities and key stakeholders within the municipality to make resources such as land and knowledge available, to develop products, test new market channels and form new strategic partnerships that support economic viable ECS. An important component of the Living Lab is the exchange between the members of the City Team, the dynamics, the knowledge transfer and the experiences, the best practices they share amongst each other to address the challenges they are set out to solve.

Rotterdam LL: The main issues for Rotterdam thus revolves around legitimacy, administrative support, possible rewards for adding value, professionalism, self-sufficiency, and organization. Rotterdam’s main objective for the Living Labs is: “Making green initiatives in the city self-supporting”. The Rotterdam living lab has three main goals at various levels of intervention: 1) Network of ECS, 2) Business development and models, 3) Facilitation of ECS by municipality. The table below lays out the relevant stakeholders and sub goals that relate to the Description of Action.

Session “Matchmaking FRC with FC and mutual learning”

Rapporteur: WP1 leader, Ferne Edwards (RMIT Europe)

Conceptualization and planning Max Manderscheid (BOKU), Thomas Wachtel and Suhana Reddy (UBER).

For the workshop, groups formed to discuss in certain slots: the *City Teams*, the *Edible City Solution*, “*my role as city team coordinator*” and *TPM/Urban planning*, to identify who has an issue, what the issue is, what has their experience been, who can resolve this and in what format can such a solution be provided.

City Teams	Who needs to provide support
<p>In the long Governance guidelines to devise:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Strategies for inclusion - for both the City Team members, the wider community and marginalised groups; ● Strategies for maintenance - to consider how to motivate people to take part and remain in the City Team? ● Models of governance structure that could suit different City Teams (ie. to other governance bodies and activities). The tasks of city teams differ between FRC and FC, as FRC perform a living lab and FC develop a masterplan. How is this reflected in the composition and working method? ● Question of elections could change state of City Team ● What are City Teams for? 	<p>Lead by WP1 with support from WP3 & 4</p>
<p>Terms of references/ Letter of commitment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● City team members are afraid to sign the ToRs, as they cannot estimate the impact of an obligation. WP1 suggested that ToRs can be adapted by City Team members and signed by city team chair and secretary at minimum. 	<p>WP1: RMIT to send out Email with Q&A’s.</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> City administration/ political representatives will not sign a binding document, but a letter of support/intent. 	
<p>Management/Administrative matters to discuss:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Many tasks/ deliverables from the project stop the process of working with developing the City Team. Which costs are eligible? E.g. are FC are allowed to use budget for practical implementation? Will there be an annual City Team meeting (i.e. different to the General Meeting)? Possible alternatives to CMT and SharePoint (as they are difficult to use) for knowledge sharing between FRC and FC: e.g. WhatsApp group or regular skype calls. How to ensure data protection? Which project data should be shared and how? 	<p>Coordinator</p> <p>WP1 and WP4: connecting FRC and FC</p> <p>WP7 and WP8 to provide short guidelines for data protection and data management.⁴</p>
<p>Knowledge sharing issues within the city teams (relating both to FRC and FC):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Difficult to gather all the City Team members at one time > some want to meet during work hours, others can't because they are voluntary members How to motivate city team members to participate continuously? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Concrete projects and practical implementation of ECS motivates people. FRC have the LL, but not FC. The work on project deliverables can discourage city team members, as these tasks are not related to their daily work. Not all members are interested in all issues. Establishment of different formats to address different issues i.e. different work streams, subgroups to focus on specific thematic. Linking public administration to local groups City Team coordinators feel isolated when working on specific tasks. Supportive knowledge sharing between Cities is desired. Social versus societal issues with regards to inclusion 	<p>Coordinator offered to assess in consultation with the EC an implementation plan for FC and to foster smaller demonstration projects to motivate participants of City Teams in FC: the FCs should write a draft for implementation (incl. budget plan) for ECS implementation to submit to Coordinator.</p> <p>RMIT in WP1 to set up monthly knowledge sharing sessions for FRC/FC to exchange experiences, issues and solutions. Coordinators to attend to provide advice.</p>
<p>Questions of FC:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> What is TPM? Is it relevant for the City Teams? Some FC need land-use maps. 	<p>WP4 to provide deliverable before January 2020 (See D4.1 and D4.2)</p> <p>WP2 to support mapping.</p>

Visit to a social garden in Sant Feliu de Llobregat

Rapporteur: Joachim Comas (ICRA)

On 24 October 2019, the annual meeting of EdiCitNet - Edible Cities Network ('Edible Cities Network') was held in Sant Feliu del Llobregat. The event brought together experts on NBS and representatives from different cities and universities from all over Europe.

After the exchange of experiences, the members of the Edicitnet consortium and the assistants of the event (representatives of the City Council and the city team) visited **the reference projects that integrate edible natural solutions** in Sant Feliu municipality, the urban and periurban gardens of the

⁴ Data management plan is D7.3.

Parc Agrari of Baix Llobregat⁵ and the **social gardens** nearby the Parc Agrari. **This ECS combines the recovery of an urban space for agriculture and labor insertion.** The visit was conducted by the director of the Solidarity Foundation of the University of Barcelona, a foundation that launched the social garden project, and a technician of the NGO Tarpuna (project manager).

EdiCitNet & friends

EdiCitNet & friends was planned as umbrella incorporating different formats of interacting between different partner acting in the field of ECS or related fields. Thus, this title should just introduce the wider scope of a bigger community aiming at the major goals social cohesion, economic resilience and ecological impact in cities. This community of knowledge and practice is no longer tied to specific target groups meeting in a filter bubble but aims at exchanging knowledge beyond disciplinary boundaries in order to open up silo-thinking and enlarge the individual scope of perception and knowledge.

The EdiCitNet & friends' session aims to gather technical, practical and local knowledge on ECS. This is a clustering format, for connecting the project EdiCitNet with other European initiatives but also with local initiatives and create a community of best practices across projects dealing with nature-based solutions and ECS. Representatives from NBS projects funded by the European Commission under Horizon 2020, and from local food-related initiatives and experts from Europe shared here their views and concerns about the transition towards the future of Edible Cities. This session was divided in two parts:

- the first one for presenting large European NBS clustered projects;
- the second one, to present local ECS initiatives.

⁵ Web: <https://parcs.diba.cat/es/web/baixllobregat/situacio-i-accessos> and <https://www.santfeliu.cat/go.faces?xmid=23894>

Session: Clustering with other NBS projects

EdiCitNet & friends first session included presentations of clustered nature-based solutions projects to look for synergies to increase impacts and enhance transfer to more sustainable, greener & better social cohesion cities. These clustered projects are the following:

- URBINAT (H2020 project). Presenter: Diego Pajarito
- Urban GreenUp (H2020 project). Presenter: Cristina Yacoub & Gemma Torres
- Urbag (ERC). Presenter: Cristina Madrid
- Circular cities COST Action. Presenter: Natasa Atanasova

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Picture 3: NBS project clustered with EdiCitNet

Session: Clustering with local initiatives in Catalunya

The second part included presentations of ECSs in practice, local initiatives and experiences. The list of the interventions was:

- Occupational and inclusive therapies - Montse Aulinas F. Ramon, Noguera
- Edible green roof - Adela Martínez, Huertos in the sky
- Pick your happiness – Kai Gildhorn, Mundraub (*)
- Social Gardens - Mallku Negre, Caritas
- Youth entrepreneurship – Helene Gallis Nabolagshager (*)
- Eco-solidarian garden - Andreu Blanchart, UdG
- Artistic and cultural education for sustainability – Roser Servalls, Carulla Foundation
- Community garden - Miki Royan & Gabriela Dimaro, ConnectHort
- School gardening - Núria Martínez & Xevi Benzal, Fund. Drissa

(*) partners in EdiCitNet.

Picture 4: Fishbowl exercise with the EdiCitNet & Friends

The fishbowl format allowed a free and open discussion and frank expressions of needs and demands. This format will be standard in the ECS Forum (see. D7.5) to be able to keep a lateral discussion mode following the overcoming of disciplinaries' boundaries. This and complementary formats will be used to support the ECS forum in future and will transfer the discussion into the virtual space on CMT.

About the EdiCitNet project

EdiCitNet is demonstrating innovative nature-based solutions (NBS). Edible City Solutions (ECS) are going one step further: We include the whole chain of urban food production, distribution and utilisation for inclusive urban regeneration and address societal challenges such as mass urbanisation, social inequality and climate change and resource protection in cities.

Thank you!

Twitter: @edicitnet

Insta: edicitnet

edicitnet-coordinator@eurtd.com

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